

RECENT APPROACHES AND REVIEW ON THE USE OF BOTANICALS FROM MEDICINAL AND AROMATIC PLANTS IN STORED GRAIN PEST MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

During storage a major portion of food grain is lost due to pests and this is a major challenge in Agriculture as various life stages of insects cause economic damage and reduce the quality of food grains and stored products. Plants are rich sources of bioactive chemicals that serve as an alternative to synthetic chemicals. Many plants have insecticidal properties that are being used in integrated pest management; on the other hand, botanical extracts and essential oils play a very important role in the control of insect pests that cause infestation of stored food products and grains and consequently the degradation of their quality. These botanicals act as repellents, toxicants, and antifeedants against insect growth, in addition to impairing ovicidal activity and causing extinction of insect eggs. The botanicals reviewed in this work include *Piper nigrum*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Vernonia amygdalina*, *Capsicum annuum*, *Ocimum gratissimum*, *Zingiber officinale*, and *Allium sativum*.

Keywords: Botanicals; Insecticidal; *Piper nigrum*; *Azadirachta indica*; *Vernonia amygdalina*; *Capsicum annuum*; *Ocimum gratissimum*; *Zingiber officinale*; *Allium sativum*

Introduction

The efficient control of stored grain pests has long been the aim of entomologists throughout the world. Synthetic chemical pesticides have been used for many years to control stored grain pests (Salem *et al.*, 2007). However, the potential hazards for mammals from synthetic insecticides, increased concern by consumers over insecticide residues in processed cereal products, the occurrence of insecticide-resistant insect strains, the ecological consequences, increasing cost of application and the precautions necessary to work with traditional chemical insecticides, call for new approaches to control stored-product insect pests (Aslam *et al.*, 2002; Udo, 2005; Fields, 2006; Salem *et al.*, 2007; Mahdian and Rahman, 2008). Therefore, there is a need to look for alternative organic sources that are readily available, cheap, affordable, relatively less poisonous and less detrimental to the environment (Udo, 2005). Peasant farmers and researchers often claim successful use of material of plant origin in insect pest control including spices and powders of plant parts (Akinneye *et al.*, 2006). Previous research indicated that some plant powders, oils and extracts have strong effects on stored grain insects such as toxicity and the inhibition of reproduction (Emeasor *et al.*, 2005; Nadra, 2006). The simplest way to apply plants to a stock of seeds is harvesting the plant and adding it to the seeds. The modes of action of powders vary, but with low to moderate dosages, the effect is always repellent or toxic, never mechanical (Rajapakse, 2006). For the last few years the influence of different plant dried materials (added as powder to the products the pests feed on) on the cereal and flour pests have been widely researched (Blazejewska & Wyrostkiewicz, 1998). The use of spices is also less costly, easily available, safer and don't do any hazard using in the stores (Aslam *et al.*, 2002; Mahdian and Rahman, 2008). A number of spices had been tried and found effective. Some include powders from red peppers (*Capsicum* spp.) and black peppers (*Piper* spp.), *Ocimum gratissimum*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Zingiber officinale*, *Allium sativum* etc.

Piper nigrum

Plants from the family Piperaceae constitute a promising source of biologically active compounds. Species within the genus *Piper* have been used medicinally for centuries in many parts of the world (Tripathi *et al.* 1996; Parmaret *et al.*, 1997), and pepper products are well tolerated by humans. The most recognized species is black pepper, *Piper nigrum* L., grown as a major spice crop in many tropical regions. The main secondary metabolites in *Piper* plants include amides, lignans, flavonoids, lactones, butenolides, cyclohexanes, and epoxides (Tripathi *et al.*, 1996). The amides are of primary interest in insect control, as they have shown a promising knock-down effect (Miya-kado *et al.*, 1979, 1980; Gbewonyo *et al.*, 1993) and also

deter feeding and oviposition (Scott *et al.*, 2003, 2004). In addition, lignans synergize the activity of other insecticides (Bernard *et al.*, 1995).

Azadiracta indica

The use of neem plant's (*Azadirachta indica*) active ingredients which exhibit agro-medicinal properties conferring insecticidal as well as immunomodulatory and anti-cancer properties. The most prominent constituent of neem is azadirachtin, which has been established as a pivotal insecticidal ingredient. It acts as an antifeedant, repellent, and repugnant agent and induces sterility in insects by preventing oviposition and interrupting sperm production in males. This review discusses, key neem pesticidal components, their active functional ingredients along with recent strategies on employing nanocarriers, to provide controlled release of the active ingredients and to improve their stability and sustainability.

Azadirachtin

The main component of neem oil, leaves, flowers, and fruits with insecticidal properties is Azadirachtin. It constitutes 0.1-0.3 % of neem seeds and was first isolated from *A. indica* by Morgan *et al.* at Keele University, England (Schmutterer, 1985). It is a complex tetranortriterpenoid limonoid with repellent and pesticidal properties. Biosynthesis of triterpenoids from *A. indica* initiates with azadirone and a C-ring opening, which culminates in Azadirachtin formation. Azadirachtin, along with other related triterpenoids such as Azadirachtin B, salannin and nimbin, are the active ingredients in neem plant based bioinsecticides and they act by disrupting the growth and development of insects and by deterring their feeding. It is considered as a botanical pesticide with exceptional growth regulating and biocidal efficacy along with deterrent effects on the ovipositing and feeding of insects (Morgan, 2009). An attempt to evaluate the exact molecular mechanism of insecticidal activity of azadirachtin on *Monochamus alternatus*, a pine sawyer beetle, has indicated enrichment of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) in 50 pathways. 920 and 9984 unique genes were found to be up and down regulated significantly. Such detailed gene profiling to assess the azadirachtin internalization with *M. alternatus*, can promote the development of efficient azadirachtin derived herbal pesticides (Lin *et al.*, 2016).

Azadirachtin is structurally similar to the insect hormones known as "ecdysones" which are responsible for metamorphosis in insects. The feeding behaviour in insects is dependent on the neural inputs received from the chemical sensors of the insects, for example, the taste receptors in the mouthparts, tarsi and oral cavity. These sensors integrate a "sensory code" that is delivered to the central nervous system. Manifestation of anti-feedancy by azadirachtin occurs through the

stimulation of deterrent cells in these chemoreceptors and by blocking the feeding stimulation in insects by firing the "sugar" receptor cells (Jennifer Mordue Luntz et al., 1998).

In addition to anti-feedancy, azadirachtin injection also leads to physiological effects in the insect's midgut, which causes a reduction in the post-ingestive digestive efficiency. This reduction in efficiency is known as "secondary" antifeedancy and is due to disturbances in the hormonal as well as physiological systems. These disturbances include hindrance in the food movement through the insect's midgut and inhibition in production of digestive enzymes (Schmutterer, 1985). An early study conducted by Nisbet *et al.* (1996) highlighted this antifeedant feature of azadirachtin. It was established that a concentration of 50-100 ppm of azadirachtin caused an insecticidal effect; however, it has a high potential to harm beneficial insects as well. Therefore, a low concentration was tested which concluded that a concentration of only 5 ppm of azadirachtin can dramatically decrease the fecundity in aphids within 48 h of feeding. Further, a diet containing more than 10 ppm azadirachtin led to the production of non-viable nymphs. Thus, it can be concluded that even with a low concentration of azadirachtin, it cannot cause an immediate antifeedancy. Secondary antifeedancy effects as well as a sterilant effect can rapidly manifest themselves and aid in providing crop protection by reducing the pest population without harming non-target or natural predator populations (Nisbet et al., 1996). Azadirachtin interferes with the growth and molting process of insects. Its ingestion leads to abnormal molts, growth reduction and increased mortalities. Azadirachtin interferes with the synthesis of an "ecdysteroid" hormone, which is responsible for the molting in insects. Indirectly, azadirachtin affects the neurosecretory system in insects by blocking the release of morphogenetic peptide hormones such as prothoracicotropic hormones that control the prothoracic glands and allatostatins, which in turn control the corpora allata (responsible for secreting juvenile hormones). Molting hormones from prothoracic glands are responsible for controlling the formation of new cuticles, and play a central role in ecdysis. The formation of juvenile stages during each molt is controlled by the juvenile hormone from the corpora allata (Nisbet, 2000). Disruption in these events by azadirachtin, leads to various sterility and molting defects. Moreover, cellular uptake of azadirachtin inhibits both cell division as well as protein synthesis thus, causing midgut cell necrosis and flaccid paralysis of muscles (Nisbet, 2000). Neem products influence fecundity in female insects in a dose-dependent manner. Azadirachtin prevents oviposition by inhibiting oogenesis and synthesis of ovarian ecdysteroid. In males, azadirachtin acts by interrupting the meiotic process responsible for sperm production (Linton *et al.*, 1997).

Vernonia amygdalina

Vernonia amygdalina, a member of the Asteraceae family, is a small shrub that grows in the tropical Africa with petiolate leaf of about 6 mm diameter and elliptic shape (Figure 1). It is

commonly called "bitter leaf" because of its bitter taste. The bitterness can, however, be abated by boiling or by soaking the leaves in several changes of water. The bitter taste is due to anti-nutritional factors such as alkaloids, saponins, tannins, and glycoside (Li et al., 1995). The plant has been used traditionally to treat sexually transmitted diseases such as gonorrhoea and malaria in rift valley and western parts of Kenya (Erasto et al., 2007) and cancer cells (Farombi, 2004). *V. amygdalina* may provide anti-oxidant benefit (khalafalla et al., 2009). The aqueous extract of this plant has been found to have cell growth inhibitory effects in prostate cancer cell line (Adebayo et al., 2014) (Sweeney et al., 2006). The plant has antihelmintic, antitumorigenic, hypoglycaemic and hypolipidaemic activity and both the leaves and the roots are used traditionally in phytomedicine to treat fever, kidney heart disease and stomach discomfort (Farombi, 2011). Many studies have shown that *V. amygdalina* extracts may strengthen the immune system through many cytokines (Igile et al., 1994). Several investigators have isolated and characterized a number of chemical compounds with potent biological activities from the leaves of *Vernonia amygdalina*. Some of the previously isolated constituents in *Vernonia amygdalina* include: sesquiterpene lactones (Igile et al., 1995), terpenoids, flavonoids like luteolin, luteolin 7-O-glucosides and luteolin 7-O-glucuronide (Jisaka et al., 1992), steroid glycosides (khalafalla et al., 2009) (Alabi et al., 2005), saponin, terpenoids and vernonioside A, B, A1, A2, A3, B2, B3 and A4 which observed to regulate growth of *Streptococcus mutans* and *Staphylococcus aureus* and common bean insect pests in field (Huang et al., 2000). *V. amygdalina* also have reported to contain large quantity of Thiamine, Pyridoxine, Ascorbic acid, Glycine, Cysteine and Casein hydrolysate significantly more than other botanicals such as *Bryophyllum pinnatum*, *Eucalyptus globules* and *Ocimum gratissimum* (Ganjian et al., 1983). Other studies have confirmed that *V. amygdalina* have toxic compounds to common bean aphids (Dunsworth et al., 1982). The most well isolated compound with the active ingredients being specified as sesquiterpene lactones containing vernodalin, vernodalol and 11,13-dihydrovernodalin, these have insecticidal properties which act as an insect feeding deterrent (Paschal et al., 2001) as shown in Figures 2(a)-(c) below. The essential oils extracted through hydro distillation of the leaves of *V. amygdalina* contained eucalyptol (1, 8 cineole, 25%), beta pinene (14.5%), myrtenal (6.5%) (Figures 2(d)-(f)) and other minority constituents while essential oil from its aerial part contained mainly alpha-muurolol (45.7%) (Hassanali et al., 1989). Other essential oil of *V. amygdalina* (0.3%) was able to protect maize from the maize weevil *Sitophilus zeamais* by reducing the number of weevil progeny production and by evoking a high repellent action against weevil without damaging the grain. The presence of these different bioactive compounds used for various purposes in *V. amygdalina* attracts researchers to quantify the efficacy of this plant in controlling insect pests such as those damaging common beans.

Capsicum annuum

Plants of the genus *Capsicum* (Solanaceae) have numerous species and varieties and have been used for many centuries as spice, vegetable and external medicine. Nutritional, metabolic and pharmacological studies have been performed, and organic compounds in fruits and seeds have been shown to be important in cancer chemo-prevention. With regard to the chemical constituents in *Capsicum* plants, many studies exist in the literature about less polar compounds such as carotenoids, fatty acids and capsaicins, while the polar ones have not been sufficiently examined (Iorizzi *et al.*, 2000). Effects of powders or extracts from *Capsicum* species on the biology and the behaviour of stored product insects, and pest control properties as toxicity, repellency or antifeedant activity, were investigated mainly in developing countries. A repellent effect of chilli powders or extracts was observed against *Callosobruchus maculatus* (F.), *Rhyzopertha dominica* (F.), *Sitophilus zeamais* Motsch. and *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst); a toxic effect was revealed against *C. maculatus*, *R. dominica*, *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.) and *Tribolium confusum* J. du Val (Morallo-Rejesus, 1987; Williams and Mansingh, 1993; Onu and Aliyu, 1995; Gakuru and Foua-Bi, 1996; El-Lakwah *et al.*, 1997). Also, *Capsicum* fruits, ground, sliced or left whole, were found effective in controlling *C. maculatus* infestations (Ofuya, 1986; Zibokere, 1994).

Ocimum gratissimum

Ocimum gratissimum Linn (Lamiaceae) is an herbaceous plant reputed for many medicinal and agronomic practices amongst Nigerian peasant farmers. *O. gratissimum* was investigated for antimicrobial activity against ten micro-organisms and for grain protectant activity against *Callosobruchus maculatus*. The phytoconstituents of the aerial part of *O. gratissimum* were extracted with 95% ethanol using the percolation method. The crude ethanol extract was further fractionated into hexane, chloroform and methanol fractions. The fractions obtained were screened for phytoconstituents, antimicrobial and grain protectant properties. Results showed that hexane fraction exhibited the highest antimicrobial activity against *Vibrio cholera* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Similarly, hexane fraction also showed the highest grain protectant activity. The other extracts of the *O. gratissimum* did not significantly inhibit both bacterial growth and grain infestation. However, the methanol fraction contains phytochemicals such as phenolic compounds associated with antioxidant properties.

Zingiber officinale

Ginger [*Zingiber officinale* (Roscoe)] is a perennial root crop that is cultivated in almost all the tropical and subtropical regions of the world (Kannan and Nair, 1965). Nigeria is currently the world's fifth largest producer and exporter of ginger especially the split-dried ginger (Arene et al., 1986). The crop is commercially grown for its aroma, and the rhizomes are used both as a spice and for medicinal purposes (Kannan and Nair, 1965). It contains up to 5% starch and 3% volatile oils with zingiberone as the main component (McGee, 2004); these essential oils give the spice its fragrance (Jakes, 2007; Ebewele and Jomoh, 1988). Other important components of ginger include acid-soft resin which is insoluble in ether and oil, gum, lignin, vegetable matter, acetic acid, acetate of potash and sulphur (Meadows, 1988; McGee, 2004). Oleoresin found in ginger is an active ingredient which aids digestion; it also serves as anti-flatulence, anti-tussive, laxative and its antacid compounds also reduce the severity and duration of chemotherapy-induced nausea (Ernst and Pittler, 2000). Ginger is widely utilized extensively for a variety of purposes such as spice in cooking, flavour in beverages and pastries (Meadows, 1988; McGee, 2004) and flavouring for cookies, crackers and cakes (Jakes, 2007). Ginger is also used for its aesthetic appeal and as a landscaping material around sub-tropical homes (McGee, 2004). The two commercial varieties commonly grown in Nigeria are the yellow ginger (also called UG 1) and the black ginger (also called UG 11). The pesticide effect of ginger essential oil was confirmed against adults and larva of *Dermestes maculatus* (adult and larva). 1.33 ml essential oil exposure of adult pesticide for 6 h caused 36.2% mortality. The larva was more sensitive than that of adults. The percentage of mortality increased with time exposure to pests with essential oil. The LD₉₀ of ginger essential oil were 12.92, 5.14 and 3.06 after 6, 12 and 18 h exposure of *D. maculatus* larva. The corresponding LD90 were 6.52, 4.64 and 4.64 in adults of *D. maculatus* (Babarinde et al., 2016).

In another experiment carried out by (Mollaei *et al.*, 2011), toxicity of *Zingiber officinale* (Roscoe) essential oil that was isolated via hydro distillation was investigated against adults of the red flour beetle, *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) and larvae of the Mediterranean flour moth, *Ephesia kuehniella* (Zell.) and Indian meal moth, *Plodia interpunctella* (Hübner). Repellency of this oil on all the three pest species adults was also studied. In determination of fumigant toxicity, the LC₅₀ value for *T. castaneum* was calculated to be 374.95 L/L air after 48 hr of exposure. As well, LC₅₀ for *E. kuehniella* and *P. interpunctella* after 9 hr were calculated 258.95 and 69.05 L/L air, respectively. In contact toxicity assay, LC so value for *E. kuehniella* and *P. interpunctella* were determined as 0.61 and 0.81 L/cm², respectively. Relationship between exposure time and oil concentration on mortality of all species indicated that mortality was increased by increasing the oil concentration and exposure time. Repellency of this oil on all the insect species was significant.

Allium sativum

There has been a heightened interest in the last few decades in plants like garlic, which have been equipped by evolution to defend themselves against invading pathogens and pests, not only because of environmental concerns trailing the use of chemically synthesized plant protection products, but also because of farmers' and consumers' preference for organic farming strategies and produce, respectively (Nwachukwu *et al.*, 2012; Slusarenko *et al.*, 2008). For many of such plants, protection against pathogens and pests often comes in the form of sulphur-containing secondary metabolites synthesized following external attacks on them (Nwachukwu *et al.*, 2012). Allicin (diallyl thiosulfinate), the major antimicrobial substance in garlic, has attracted the attention of investigators because of its widely acclaimed potency. Garlic is known for its positive effect on health particularly the prevention of cardiovascular diseases and certain digestive cancers (Lalla *et al.*, 2013). Previous studies have shown that garlic also possesses some insecticidal, fungicidal, acaricidal, nematocidal and bactericidal properties (Lalla *et al.*, 2013). With a widespread antimicrobial activity comparable to those of common antibiotics like ampicillin (Curtis *et al.*, 2004) and penicillin (Cavallito *et al.*, 1944), it is hardly surprising that this compound has shown activity against some of the world's most notable plant pathogens including *Phytophthora infestans* and *Pseudoperonospora cubensis* (Portz *et al.*, 2008). Allicin is a phytoanticipin which means that its synthesis, from preformed precursors already present in garlic, occurs prior to any external attack or irritation, and so does not involve any expenditure of energy (Nwachukwu *et al.*, 2012; van Etten *et al.*, 1994). Allicin is formed as a volatile organosulfur compound following the disruption of garlic tissues either by crushing, piercing, or wounding. The substrate alliin (S-allyl-L-cysteine sulfoxide) held in the cytosol prior to tissue disruption reacts with the now liberated vacuolar enzyme, alliinase to give allicin with pyruvate and ammonia as by-product.

Conclusion

Evaluations have been done by many Authors on the Insecticidal properties of plant botanicals on various species of stored products insect pests. The result vividly shows that developing methods for grain protectants with decreased use of synthetic chemical insecticides is achievable. The main advantages of botanical pesticides are, environmentally friendly, easily biodegradable in other word it has no residual effect, cheap and available to small scale farmers. So, it is preferable to use plant botanicals as pesticides instead of synthetic pesticides and the botanical pesticides are recognized by organic crop producers in industrialized countries. So, the use of botanical insecticides is recommended and being promoted and research is being conducted to discover new sources of botanical insecticides.

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